

Realisability of Global Models of Interaction (Extended Version)

Maurice H. ter Beek¹

¹ ISTI-CNR, Pisa, Italy, maurice.terbeek@isti.cnr.it

² Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Germany, hennicker@ifi.lmu.de

³ CISTER & University of Porto, Portugal, jose.proenca@fc.up.pt

Abstract. We consider *global models* of communicating agents specified as transition systems labelled by *interactions* in which multiple senders and receivers can participate. A *realisation* of such a model is a set of local transition systems—one per agent—which are executed concurrently using synchronous communication. Our core challenge is how to check whether a global model is realisable and, if it is, how to synthesise a realisation. We identify and compare two variants to realise global interaction models, both relying on bisimulation equivalence. Then we investigate, for both variants, *realisability conditions* to be checked on global models. We propose a synthesis method for the construction of realisations by grouping locally indistinguishable states. The paper is accompanied by a tool that implements realisability checks and synthesises realisations.

1 Introduction

We consider the development of systems of collaborating computing entities which interact by message exchange, like communicating component systems, multi-agent systems (MAS), collective adaptive systems (CAS), groupware systems, multi-party sessions, etc. Such systems are often presented by a set of components whose local behaviour is formally described by labelled transition systems (LTS) or process expressions. Their interaction behaviour is then captured by (synchronous or asynchronous) parallel composition of the local models.

Before designing such local models it is, however, safer to first model the interaction behaviour of the components from a *global* perspective. This belief led to the investigation of various forms of global models, like global (session) types [6, 11, 23], global choreographies [35] and global languages [2]; also message sequence charts [19] and UML interaction diagrams [13, 30] serve this purpose.

An important question is, of course, whether a global model \mathcal{M} is indeed realisable by a system $\mathcal{S} = (\mathcal{M}_i)_{i \in \mathcal{I}}$ of local component models \mathcal{M}_i (where \mathcal{I} ranges over a set of component names). Possible solutions are investigated for global languages in [2] and, for global session types, in various papers (see above) by imposing syntactic restrictions on global types. These approaches use projections to generate local models from global ones.

Fig. 1: Workflow for the development of interaction-based systems

A different idea is to provide, instead of a global model, a requirements specification Sp describing properties of the desired global interaction behaviour by means of some logical formalism like in [7, 21, 22]. Then local models \mathcal{M}_i are constructed from scratch and their (synchronous) composition $\otimes(\mathcal{M}_i)_{i \in I}$ must be proven to satisfy the requirements of Sp .

From Requirements to Realisations We combine the advantages of logical specifications and global models for interaction-based systems by using both in a stepwise manner. Our development method is summarised in Fig. 1.

We start by providing a (*system*) *signature* $\Sigma = (I, M)$, which determines finite sets I of component names and M of message names. Σ induces the set $\Gamma(\Sigma)$ of (*global*) Σ -*interactions* of the form $\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ where out and in are disjoint sets of component names (such that $\text{out} \cup \text{in} \neq \emptyset$) and $\mathbf{m} \in M$. The multi-interaction $\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ expresses that all components of out send message \mathbf{m} to all components of in such that all send and receive events occur simultaneously. Since usually not all interactions in $\Gamma(\Sigma)$ are desired in an application context (one may wish, e.g., to consider only binary or multicast communication) we consider pairs (Σ, Γ) where $\Gamma \subseteq \Gamma(\Sigma)$ is a user-defined *interaction set* which restricts the set of all Σ -interactions to admissible ones. For logical specifications of global interaction behaviour, we propose an action-based logic following a dynamic-logic style which has been successfully applied for specifying ensembles (cf., e.g., [22]). The logic uses the usual diamond and box modalities of dynamic logic ($\langle \alpha \rangle \varphi$ and $[\alpha] \varphi$, resp.) which range over (structured) interactions α built over Γ by sequential composition, choice and iteration. A *global interaction-behaviour specification* is then a triple $Sp = (\Sigma, \Gamma, Ax)$, where Ax is a set of formulas, called *axioms*, expressing requirements for the global interaction behaviour (e.g., safety and liveness properties and/or desired and forbidden interaction scenarios).

Given a (global) requirements specification $Sp = (\Sigma, \Gamma, Ax)$, we construct a global model \mathcal{M} for the system's intended interaction behaviour. To formalise such models we use *global LTS* whose transitions are labelled by interactions according to Γ . If only binary interactions are admitted a global LTS is a choreography automaton as in [1]. Of course, we must check that the constructed global LTS \mathcal{M} satisfies the requirements of the specification Sp , i.e. $\mathcal{M} \models Ax$.

The central part of our work concerns the realisation (decomposition) of a global LTS \mathcal{M} in terms of a (possibly distributed) system of interacting components whose individual behaviour is modelled by *local LTS*. First we must determine, for each component name $i \in I$, which local actions component i should

provide. To do so, any interaction in which i participates must be mapped to an appropriate local action for component i . We study two variants. The first follows approaches to multi-party session types and choreography languages where the names of the communication partners are kept in local actions. For instance, a binary interaction $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$ leads to a local output action $ij! \mathbf{m}$ for i and a local input action $ij? \mathbf{m}$ for j . In approaches to component-based development, however, transitions describing local behaviour are often labelled just by message names accompanied by information whether it is an output or an input of a component. This makes components better reusable and supports interface-based design [3, 15, 26, 28]. In this case, a binary interaction $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$ leads to a local output action $! \mathbf{m}$ for i and a local input action $? \mathbf{m}$ for j . In this paper, we generalise both localisation styles to deal with multi-interactions and call the former “rich local actions” and the latter “poor local actions”. From a software designer’s point of view the poor localisation style better supports the principle of loose coupling, whereas the rich style better avoids undesired synchronisations.

Once a localisation style $x \in \{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}\}$ is chosen (\mathbf{r} for “rich” and \mathbf{p} for “poor”) one can proceed with the actual construction of a realisation of \mathcal{M} in terms of a system presented by a family $\mathcal{S} = (\mathcal{M}_i^x)_{i \in I}$ of local LTS. We say that \mathcal{M} is *realisable* (with localisation style x) if such a system exists such that \mathcal{M} is bisimilar (denoted by \sim) to the synchronous composition $\otimes_{\Gamma}^x (\mathcal{M}_i^x)_{i \in I}$ of all \mathcal{M}_i^x taking into account the interactions Γ and the localisation style x . Hence, our realisation notion is generic w.r.t. Γ and parametrised by the chosen localisation style. We show that realisability with poor local actions implies realisability with rich local actions (Theorem 2) but the converse does not hold (Example 4). Since our realisability notion is based on bisimilarity we can deal with non-deterministic behaviour, differently from language-based approaches like [2, 11].

Race Example We illustrate our methodology outlined so far by developing a (small) system, called **Race**, which is meant to model the competition of two runner components **R1** and **R2** under the control of a third component **Ctrl**. To start, we provide a signature $\Sigma_{\text{Race}} = (I_{\text{Race}}, M_{\text{Race}})$ with component names $I_{\text{Race}} = \{\mathbf{R1}, \mathbf{R2}, \mathbf{Ctrl}\}$ and message names $M_{\text{Race}} = \{\mathbf{start}, \mathbf{finish}\}$. The idea is that the controller starts the two runners simultaneously, while each runner signals individually to the controller when it has finished its run. Therefore, we use the interaction set on the left of Fig. 2. We do not model the actual running of a runner component, which would be an internal action (cf. [5]).

We require that no runner should finish before starting and that any started runner should be able to finish running. This will be expressed by dynamic logic formulas to be detailed in the requirements specification Sp_{Race} in Example 1.

Fig. 2: Interaction set Γ_{Race} (left) and global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ (right); we write **Ctrl** for $\{\mathbf{Ctrl}\}$ and similarly for **R1**, **R2**.

Table 1: Local LTS for each localisation style and for each component

Next we construct the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ shown on the right of Fig. 2, which models the required interaction behaviour of the system so that the requirements of the specification are satisfied. The system starts in the initial (global) state 0, where the controller **starts** both runners at once. Each runner separately sends a **finish** signal to the controller (in arbitrary order). After that a new run can **start**.

Finally, we want to realise the system by three local LTS such that their composition is bisimilar to the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$. We distinguish the two variants.

Rich Local Actions From Γ_{Race} we derive the following sets of rich local actions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{\text{Ctrl}}^r &= \{ \text{Ctrl } \{R1, R2\} !\text{start}, R1 \text{ Ctrl } ?\text{finish}, R2 \text{ Ctrl } ?\text{finish} \}, \\
 A_{R1}^r &= \{ \text{Ctrl } \{R1, R2\} ?\text{start}, R1 \text{ Ctrl} !\text{finish} \}, \text{ and} \\
 A_{R2}^r &= \{ \text{Ctrl } \{R1, R2\} ?\text{start}, R2 \text{ Ctrl} !\text{finish} \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For each $i \in \{\text{Ctrl}, R1, R2\}$, we use the local LTS \mathcal{M}_i^r in the upper row of Table 1 to build the system $\mathcal{S}_{\text{Race}}^r = \{\mathcal{M}_{\text{Ctrl}}^r, \mathcal{M}_{R1}^r, \mathcal{M}_{R2}^r\}$ with rich local actions. One can prove that the “rich” composition (Definition 5) of the three LTS by synchronisation w.r.t. Γ_{Race} is bisimilar (even isomorphic) to $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$; i.e., we have found a realisation with rich local actions.

Poor Local Actions In this case, we derive from Γ_{Race} the following sets of poor local actions, where information on communication partners is omitted:

$$A_{\text{Ctrl}}^p = \{ !\text{start}, ?\text{finish} \} \text{ and } A_{R1}^p = A_{R2}^p = \{ ?\text{start}, !\text{finish} \}.$$

For each $i \in \{\text{Ctrl}, R1, R2\}$, we use the local LTS \mathcal{M}_i^p in the lower row of Table 1 to build the system $\mathcal{S}_{\text{Race}}^p = \{\mathcal{M}_{\text{Ctrl}}^p, \mathcal{M}_{R1}^p, \mathcal{M}_{R2}^p\}$ with poor local actions. Also the “poor” composition (Definition 8) of the three LTS by synchronisation w.r.t. Γ_{Race} is bisimilar (even isomorphic) to $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$.

Checking Realisability, Local Quotients, and System Synthesis So far, we considered the case in which the realisation of a global interaction model \mathcal{M} is “invented”. However, there might be no realisation of \mathcal{M} and it would be better to know this as soon as possible to align the global model. Next, we consider the following two important issues and proceed as shown in Fig. 3.

1. How to check whether a given global LTS \mathcal{M} is realisable (rich/poor case)?
2. If it is, how can we build/synthesise a concrete realisation S (rich/poor case)?

Fig. 3: Approach to check realisability and system synthesis

To tackle the first question we propose, similarly to [12], to find a family $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ of equivalence relations on the global state space Q of \mathcal{M} such that, for each component name $i \in I$ and states $q, q' \in Q$, $q \equiv_i q'$ expresses that q and q' are not distinguishable from the viewpoint of i . This suggests that q and q' , though globally different, can be locally interpreted as the same states. In particular, it is required that any two states q and q' which are related by a global transition $q \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'$ should be indistinguishable for any $i \in I$ which does not participate in the interaction, i.e. $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. On the basis of a given I -equivalence \equiv , we formulate realisability conditions $\text{RC}(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$ and $\text{RC}(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^p$ for both localisation styles. For instance, consider a binary interaction $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$. Then, in the rich case, it is required that whenever there are states $q_i, q_j \in Q$ and a “glue state” $g \in Q$ such that $q_i \equiv_i g$ and $q_j \equiv_j g$ and if there are global transitions $q_i \xrightarrow{i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'_i$ and $q_j \xrightarrow{i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'_j$, then, since $q_i \equiv_i g$, the rich local action $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$ should be enabled in the “local i -view” on g and, similarly, since $q_j \equiv_j g$, action $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$ should be enabled in the “local j -view” on g . As a consequence, there should also be a global transition $q_i \xrightarrow{i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'_i$ such that $q'_i \equiv_i g'$ and $q'_j \equiv_j g'$. The “realisability condition” for the poor case is stronger since communication partners are abstracted away when moving from global interactions to poor local actions. Thus in the condition above one must consider not only transitions $q_i \xrightarrow{i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'_i$ and $q_j \xrightarrow{i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'_j$, with the same interaction $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$, but also arbitrary other ones in which i is the sender of \mathbf{m} when moving from q_i to q'_i and j is the receiver of \mathbf{m} when moving from q_j to q'_j .

We show that in the rich and in the poor case our condition is sufficient for realisability (cf. Theorems 3 and 4).

In both cases, the principle idea how to synthesise a realisation is the same. Given a family $(\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ of I -equivalences for which the realisability condition holds, we construct, for each $i \in I$, a local quotient $(\mathcal{M} / \equiv_i)^{r/p}$ by identifying global states (in \mathcal{M}) which are i -equivalent. Thus we get the desired system (which might still benefit from minimisations w.r.t. bisimilarity).

Note that the I -equivalences found for satisfying the realisability condition in the rich case may not be the same as in the poor case and thus also the local quotients may show different behaviour. Moreover, the technique of building local quotients differs from projections used in the field of multi-party session types, since projections are partial operations depending on syntactic conditions (cf., e.g., [6]). A less syntactic and more expressive approach is proposed in [25].

As an example, recall the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ shown in Fig. 2 (right). The three local LTS with *rich* local actions shown in the upper row of Table 1 are, up to renaming of states, local quotients of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$. To construct the local quotient for R1, global states 0 and 2 are identified, as well as states 1 and 3 (and symmet-

rically for the local quotient for **R2**). For **Ctrl**, no proper identification is applied (cf. [Example 5](#) for details). Also the three local LTS with *poor* local actions in the lower row of [Table 1](#) are, up to renaming of states, local quotients of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$. In this case, however, to construct the local quotient for **Ctrl**, two global states of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ are identified, namely states 2 and 3 (cf. [Example 9](#) for details).

Contributions and Related Work

1. We propose a rigorous discipline for developing interaction-based systems following a step-wise development method from dynamic-logic requirements specifications over global models of interaction down to systems of (possibly distributed) components. Thus our approach supplements approaches to realisations of global behaviour descriptions (in the form of global languages, e.g. [2], or global session types, e.g. [23]), by an abstract logical layer.
2. Our approach is driven by specified sets of multi-interactions supporting any kind of synchronous communication between multiple senders and multiple receivers. To the best of our knowledge, realisations of global models with arbitrary multi-interactions have not yet been studied in the literature.
3. Our correctness notion for realisation of global models by systems of communicating local components is based on bisimulation, thus letting us deal with non-determinism and going beyond language-based approaches like [2, 11]. Bisimulation also fits well with global requirements specifications since dynamic logic formulas are invariant under bisimulation and therefore hold in any realisation of a global model of a global specification.
4. For constructing realisations we consider two localisation styles (rich and poor local actions) and analyse their relationship. This is a novel result.
5. A global interaction model may, in general, not be realisable. We provide conditions for realisability with respect to both localisation styles. Our conditions are related to the work in [12] which, however, does not deal with multi-interactions and uses a stronger condition ensuring realisation up to isomorphism of LTS; cf. our discussion in [Sect. 5.1](#).
6. For realisable global models, we construct realisations in terms of systems of local quotients. Similar quotient constructions have been used in the proofs of [12], but not for multi-interactions and for different localisation styles. The technique of building local quotients differs from projections used in the field of multi-party session types, since projections are partial operations depending on syntactic conditions (cf., e.g., [6]). In our approach, no restrictions on the form of global models are assumed. However, it must be said that the syntactic restrictions used for global types guarantee some kind of communication properties of a resulting system which we do not consider.
7. We developed a prototypical tool Ceta which checks realisability conditions and, if they are satisfied, generates local quotients and hence realisations.

Outline After some formal preliminaries in [Sect. 2](#), we show how to specify requirements for global models of interaction in [Sect. 3](#) and how to realise the latter in [Sect. 4](#). The conditions that guarantee realisability are studied in [Sect. 5](#).

In Sect. 6, we present a tool that implements our analyses. It is available at <https://lmf.di.uminho.pt/ceta> and all examples of the paper are predefined in the tool, like $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$, including a hyperlink to open the tool with the specific example. Sect. 7 wraps up the paper.

2 Formal Preliminaries

2.1 Labelled Transition Systems and Bisimulation

Let A be a finite set of actions. A *labelled transition system* (LTS) over A is a tuple $\mathcal{L} = (Q, q_0, A, T)$ such that Q is a finite set of states, $q_0 \in Q$ is the initial state, and $T \subseteq Q \times A \times Q$ is a transition relation. Note that we consider finite-state LTS, which makes the realisability conditions presented later *decidable*. We write $q \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\mathcal{L}} q'$, or shortly $q \xrightarrow{\alpha} q'$, to denote $(q, \alpha, q') \in T$. For $A' \subseteq A$, we write $q \xrightarrow{A'}^* q'$ if there exist $q \xrightarrow{a_1} q_1 \xrightarrow{a_2} \dots \xrightarrow{a_n} q'$ for some $n \geq 0$ and $a_1, \dots, a_n \in A'$. A state $q \in Q$ is *reachable by A'* if $q_0 \xrightarrow{A'}^* q$; it is *reachable* if $q_0 \xrightarrow{A}^* q$. The set of reachable states of \mathcal{L} is denoted by $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{L})$.

For expressing behavioural equivalence of LTS we use the standard notion of (strong) bisimulation: Let $\mathcal{L}_i = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, A, T_i)$ be two LTS (for $i = 1, 2$) over the same action set A . A *bisimulation relation* between \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 is a relation $B \subseteq Q_1 \times Q_2$ such that for all $(q_1, q_2) \in B$ and for all $a \in A$ the following holds:

1. if $q_1 \xrightarrow{a}_{\mathcal{L}_1} q'_1$ then there exist $q'_2 \in Q_2$ and $q_2 \xrightarrow{a}_{\mathcal{L}_2} q'_2$ such that $(q'_1, q'_2) \in B$;
2. if $q_2 \xrightarrow{a}_{\mathcal{L}_2} q'_2$ then there exist $q'_1 \in Q_1$ and $q_1 \xrightarrow{a}_{\mathcal{L}_1} q'_1$ such that $(q'_1, q'_2) \in B$.

\mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 are *bisimilar*, denoted by $\mathcal{L}_1 \sim \mathcal{L}_2$, if there exists a bisimulation relation B between \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 such that $(q_{1,0}, q_{2,0}) \in B$.

2.2 Dynamic Logic

We use (test-free) propositional dynamic logic (PDL) [18] to formulate behavioural properties. Let A be a finite set of (*atomic*) actions. The set $Act(A)$ of *structured actions* over A is defined by the grammar

$$\alpha := a \mid \alpha; \alpha \mid \alpha + \alpha \mid \alpha^* \quad (\text{actions})$$

with $a \in A$, sequential composition $;$, nondeterministic choice $+$, and iteration $*$. If $A = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$, we write *some* for the structured action $a_1 + \dots + a_n$. We may also refer to all actions of A but one, say a , and express this by $-a$.

The set $Frm(A)$ of *A-formulas* is defined by the grammar

$$\varphi := true \mid \neg\varphi \mid \varphi \vee \varphi \mid \langle \alpha \rangle \varphi \quad (\text{formulas})$$

where $\alpha \in Act(A)$. Formula $\langle \alpha \rangle \varphi$ expresses that at the current state it is possible to execute α such that φ holds in the next state.

Abbreviations We use the usual abbreviations like *false*, $\varphi \wedge \varphi'$, $\varphi \rightarrow \varphi'$, and the modal box operator $[\alpha]\varphi$ which stands for $\neg\langle\alpha\rangle\neg\varphi$ and expresses that whenever in the current state α is executed, then φ holds afterwards.

For the interpretation of formulas we use LTS. Let $\mathcal{L} = (Q, q_0, A, T)$ be an LTS over A . First we extend the transition relation of \mathcal{L} to structured actions in $Act(A)$ defined inductively by:

$$\begin{aligned} q &\xrightarrow{\alpha_1;\alpha_2}_{\mathcal{L}} q' \text{ if there exists } \hat{q} \in Q \text{ such that } q \xrightarrow{\alpha_1}_{\mathcal{L}} \hat{q} \text{ and } \hat{q} \xrightarrow{\alpha_2}_{\mathcal{L}} q', \\ q &\xrightarrow{\alpha_1+\alpha_2}_{\mathcal{L}} q' \text{ if } q \xrightarrow{\alpha_1}_{\mathcal{L}} q' \text{ or } q \xrightarrow{\alpha_2}_{\mathcal{L}} q', \\ q &\xrightarrow{\alpha^*}_{\mathcal{L}} q' \text{ if } q = q' \text{ or there exists } \hat{q} \in Q \text{ such that } q \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\mathcal{L}} \hat{q} \text{ and } \hat{q} \xrightarrow{\alpha^*}_{\mathcal{L}} q'. \end{aligned}$$

The *satisfaction* of a formula $\varphi \in Frm(A)$ by \mathcal{L} at a state $q \in Q$, denoted by $\mathcal{L}, q \models \varphi$, is inductively defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}, q &\models \text{true}, \\ \mathcal{L}, q &\models \neg\varphi \text{ if not } \mathcal{L}, q \models \varphi, \\ \mathcal{L}, q &\models \varphi_1 \vee \varphi_2 \text{ if } \mathcal{L}, q \models \varphi_1 \text{ or } \mathcal{L}, q \models \varphi_2, \\ \mathcal{L}, q &\models \langle\alpha\rangle\varphi \text{ if there exists } q' \in Q \text{ such that } q \xrightarrow{\alpha}_{\mathcal{L}} q' \text{ and } \mathcal{L}, q' \models \varphi. \end{aligned}$$

\mathcal{L} *satisfies* a formula $\varphi \in Frm(A)$, written $\mathcal{L} \models \varphi$, if $\mathcal{L}, q_0 \models \varphi$. Hence, for the satisfaction of a formula by an LTS the non-reachable states are irrelevant.

We deviate from the classical semantics of PDL [18], since we use LTS *with initial states* as models to interpret satisfaction of formulas. This is because we are interested in the formulation of properties of systems of (concurrently running, interacting) components. In particular, we can express safety properties, like $[some^*]\varphi$, and some kinds of liveness properties like, e.g., $[some^*]\langle some^*; a \rangle\varphi$.

Satisfaction of formulas in PDL is invariant under bisimulation [8] and also the Hennessy–Milner Theorem [20] can be extended to PDL (since Hennessy–Milner logic is a sublogic of PDL).

Theorem 1. *Let $\mathcal{L}_i = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, A, T_i)$ be two LTS over A for $i = 1, 2$.*

1. *If $\mathcal{L} \sim \mathcal{L}'$ then, for any $\varphi \in Frm(A)$, $\mathcal{L} \models \varphi$ iff $\mathcal{L}' \models \varphi$.*
2. *If, for any $\varphi \in Frm(A)$, $\mathcal{L} \models \varphi$ iff $\mathcal{L}' \models \varphi$ and \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 are image finite⁴ then $\mathcal{L} \sim \mathcal{L}'$.*

3 Specify Requirements for Global Models of Interaction

In this work, we focus on the stepwise development of systems whose components interact by synchronous message exchange. We support “multi-interactions”, in which several named senders and named receivers may participate in a communication. Our starting point are *signatures* $\Sigma = (I, M)$, where I is a finite set of component names (called participants in the theory of multi-party sessions [6, 11, 23]) and M is a finite set of message names. Any signature Σ induces a set $\Gamma(\Sigma)$ of (global) Σ -interactions defined by

$$\Gamma(\Sigma) = \{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m} \mid \text{out}, \text{in} \subseteq I, \text{out} \cup \text{in} \neq \emptyset, \mathbf{m} \in M\}.$$

⁴ This means that in any state there are at most finitely many outgoing transitions labelled with the same action.

We define the set of *participants* in a Σ -interaction $\gamma = \text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ by $\text{ptc}(\gamma) = \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. An interaction $\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ expresses that all components whose name occurs in out send a message named \mathbf{m} to all components whose name occurs in in . Such interactions involving arbitrarily many senders and receivers are also called *multi-interactions*. They will be interpreted by **synchronous** (handshake) communication where the interacting components participate simultaneously. As a shorthand notation we write i for $\{i\}$. Special cases are binary interactions between two components i, j , written $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$, or multicast communication with one sender i and a group in of receivers, written $i \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$.

Usually not all Σ -interactions are meaningful for a certain application. Therefore we consider pairs (Σ, Γ) such that $\Gamma \subseteq \Gamma(\Sigma)$ restricts the set of Σ -interactions to *admissible* ones (e.g., binary interactions). Γ is called an *interaction set*.

General Assumption In the sequel, we assume that (Σ, Γ) denotes a system signature $\Sigma = (I, M)$ together with an interaction set Γ . When we talk about a signature we always mean a system signature.

We propose to use interactions as atomic actions in dynamic logic formulas for specifying desired and forbidden interaction properties from a global perspective.

Definition 1 (global Sp). A global interaction behaviour specification is a triple $Sp = (\Sigma, \Gamma, Ax)$ where $Ax \subseteq \text{Frm}(\Gamma)$ is a set of Γ -formulas, called axioms.

Example 1. A requirements specification for the interaction behaviour of the **Race** system is given by $Sp_{\text{Race}} = (\Sigma_{\text{Race}}, \Gamma_{\text{Race}}, Ax_{\text{Race}})$ where Σ_{Race} and Γ_{Race} are defined in Sect. 1 and Ax_{Race} consists of the following two dynamic logic formulas expressing the two informal requirements described in Sect. 1.

1. “No runner should finish before it has been started by the controller.”

$$\left[\left(- (\text{Ctrl} \rightarrow \{\text{R1}, \text{R2}\} : \text{start}) \right)^* ; \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{R1} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish} + \\ \text{R2} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish} \end{array} \right) \right] \text{false}$$

2. “For any started runner it should be possible to finish its run.”

$$\left[\text{some}^* ; \text{Ctrl} \rightarrow \{\text{R1}, \text{R2}\} : \text{start} \right] \left(\begin{array}{l} \langle \text{some}^* ; \text{R1} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish} \rangle \text{true} \wedge \\ \langle \text{some}^* ; \text{R2} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish} \rangle \text{true} \end{array} \right) \quad \triangleright$$

Given a requirements specification Sp , the goal of our next step is to model the global interaction behaviour of the intended system in accordance with Sp . This is more reliable than directly going to a system implementation of Sp with various components whose concurrent behaviour might be difficult to grasp. The idea of modelling global behaviour first can be found in many proposals, for instance in the area of (global) session types (cf., e.g., [24]), and also in the context of telecommunication systems modelled by message sequence charts [19]. Our approach has been inspired by the use of choreography automata in [1]. We, however, do not restrict ourselves to binary communication but allow arbitrary multi-interactions. Formally, we model global interaction behaviour by LTS with (global) interactions from Γ on the transitions.

Definition 2 (global LTS). A global LTS over (Σ, Γ) is defined as an LTS $\mathcal{M} = (Q, q_0, \Gamma, T)$ over Γ .

Once a global interaction model \mathcal{M} for a requirements specification $Sp = (\Sigma, \Gamma, Ax)$ is constructed, it remains to verify that \mathcal{M} is correct w.r.t. Sp , i.e. that all axioms in Ax are satisfied by \mathcal{M} . For this we may use the mCRL2 toolset [10] and, as explained in [5], the translation of LTS to process expressions as well as the translation of our dynamic logic formulas to the syntax used by mCRL2.

Example 2. The global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ provided for interactions in the race example from Sect. 1 satisfies the axioms of the specification Sp_{Race} (cf. Example 1). \triangleright

4 Realisations of Global Models of Interaction

A crucial step in our development method concerns the realisation of a global interaction model in terms of a system of (possibly distributed) components modelled by *local* LTS (cf. Fig. 1). In this section, we formally define what we mean by a realisation. We study two variants obeying different localisation styles.

For modelling local components we must first determine, for each component name $i \in I$, which are the local actions that component i is supposed to support. There are at least two possibilities but, in any case, it is clear that only global interactions in Γ which involve i , either as a sender or as a receiver, are relevant to induce a local action for i . For an interaction $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$ this means that either $i \in \text{out}$ or $i \in \text{in}$. It may, however, be discussed whether the other component names occurring in out or in should be kept in the local action regarding message \mathbf{m} for i or whether they should be removed such that only the message name \mathbf{m} is kept together with the information whether \mathbf{m} is an output or an input of i . In the following we will consider both variants since they lead to different instantiations of our notion of realisability and to different realisability conditions considered hereafter in Sect. 5.

4.1 Realisations Using Rich Local Actions

It is quite common in approaches to global (session) types and choreography languages to preserve the names of communication partners when moving from global interactions to local actions. For instance, in [2], a binary interaction $i \rightarrow j : \mathbf{m}$ leads to a local output action $ij!\mathbf{m}$ for i and a local input action $ij?\mathbf{m}$ for j . We generalise this approach to the case of multi-interactions and call the resulting local actions *rich*.

Definition 3 (rich local actions and local LTS). For each $i \in I$, the set of rich local i -actions derived from Γ is $A_i^r(\Gamma) = A_{i,\text{out}}^r(\Gamma) \cup A_{i,\text{in}}^r(\Gamma)$ where

$$\begin{aligned} A_{i,\text{out}}^r(\Gamma) &= \{\text{out in}!\mathbf{m} \mid \exists (\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \text{ such that } i \in \text{out}\} \text{ and} \\ A_{i,\text{in}}^r(\Gamma) &= \{\text{out in}?\mathbf{m} \mid \exists (\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \text{ such that } i \in \text{in}\}. \end{aligned}$$

A local LTS for i with rich local actions is an LTS $\mathcal{M}_i^r = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, A_i^r(\Gamma), T_i)$.

Definition 4 (system with rich local actions). A system over (Σ, Γ) with rich local actions is a family $\mathcal{S}^r = (\mathcal{M}_i^r)_{i \in I}$ of local LTS \mathcal{M}_i^r over $A_i^r(\Gamma)$ for $i \in I$.

The behaviour of such a system is modelled by the parallel Γ -composition of its components \mathcal{M}_i^r ($i \in I$) such that for all interactions $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$ a global transition exists in the current global state of the composition if for all $i \in \text{out}$ ($i \in \text{in}$ resp.) there is a transition in \mathcal{M}_i^r with the local action $\text{out in}! \mathbf{m}$ ($\text{out in} ? \mathbf{m}$ resp.) leaving the current local state of \mathcal{M}_i^r .

Definition 5 (synchronous Γ -composition with rich local actions). *Let $(\mathcal{M}_i^r)_{i \in I}$ be a family of local LTS $\mathcal{M}_i^r = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, A_i^r(\Gamma), T_i)$ with rich local actions. The synchronous Γ -composition of $(\mathcal{M}_i^r)_{i \in I}$ with rich local actions is the global LTS, denoted by $\otimes_{\Gamma}^r (\mathcal{M}_i^r)_{i \in I}$, over (Σ, Γ) with initial state $(q_{i,0})_{i \in I}$ and with (product) states $(q_i)_{i \in I}$ (with $q_i \in Q$ for all $i \in I$) and transitions generated from the initial state by the following rule:*

$$\frac{(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \quad \forall i \in \text{out} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{out in}! \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}_i^r} q'_i \quad \forall i \in \text{in} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{out in} ? \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}_i^r} q'_i}{(q_i)_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}^r (\mathcal{M}_i^r)_{i \in I}} (q'_i)_{i \in I} \text{ where } q'_i = q_i \text{ for all } i \in I \setminus (\text{out} \cup \text{in})}$$

Definition 6 (realisability with rich local actions). *Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) . A system $\mathcal{S} = (\mathcal{M}_i^r)_{i \in I}$ over (Σ, Γ) with rich local actions is a (rich) realisation of \mathcal{M} , if $\mathcal{M} \sim \otimes_{\Gamma}^r (\mathcal{M}_i^r)_{i \in I}$ are bisimilar. \mathcal{M} is realisable with rich local actions if such a realisation exists.*

A realisation with rich local actions for the race example is shown in Sect. 1.

Our realisability notion relies on bisimulation. Thus we are able to deal with non-determinism. In particular, according to the invariance of dynamic logic under bisimulation (see Sect. 2), we know that global models and their realisations satisfy the same formulas. Hence, once a global model of a global specification is provided, any realisation will be correct with respect to the global specification.

Example 3. We consider a simplistic non-deterministic example which points out the difference to approaches where realisability is based on language equivalence (like, e.g., [2]). There are two participants, a **Person** and a **Coin**. The person can **toss** the **Coin**, which may show **head** or **tail**. **Coin** tossing is modelled as a non-deterministic action which can lead to either **head** or **tail** (cf. [29]). Formally, $\Sigma_{\text{Toss}} = (\{\text{Person}, \text{Coin}\}, \{\text{toss}, \text{head}, \text{tail}\})$, $\Gamma_{\text{Toss}} = \{\text{Person} \rightarrow \text{Coin} : \text{toss}, \text{Coin} \rightarrow \text{Person} : \text{head}, \text{Coin} \rightarrow \text{Person} : \text{tail}\}$ and the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Toss}}$ given in Table 2. We realise $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Toss}}$ by a system consisting of the two LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Coin}}^r$ and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Person}}^r$ with rich local actions given in Table 2. Obviously, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Toss}} \sim \otimes_{\Gamma_{\text{Toss}}}^r \{\mathcal{M}_{\text{Coin}}^r, \mathcal{M}_{\text{Person}}^r\}$.

Table 2: Non-deterministic toss of a **Coin** by a **Person**

We cannot provide a deterministic version for both the **Person** and **Coin** components since then the required bisimulation could not be established. \triangleright

4.2 Realisations Using Poor Local Actions

Now we consider an approach where we omit the communication partners when we move from a global multi-interaction $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$ to a local action. In this case only the message name \mathbf{m} is kept together with output information $!\mathbf{m}$ for $i \in \text{out}$ and input information $?\mathbf{m}$ for $i \in \text{in}$. This complies with the idea of component automata used in teams [3–5] and many other approaches to component-based design (e.g., I/O automata [28] and interface automata [15]) where local actions of components are just given by their names (possibly with some data parameters) and input/output information. We call the resulting local actions “poor” since they do not (locally) constrain the communication partners which allows for more flexible ways of bindings.

Definition 7 (poor local actions and local LTS). *For each $i \in I$, the set of poor local i -actions derived from Γ is given by $\Lambda_i^p(\Gamma) = \Lambda_{i,\text{out}}^p(\Gamma) \cup \Lambda_{i,\text{in}}^p(\Gamma)$ where*

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_{i,\text{out}}^p(\Gamma) &= \{!\mathbf{m} \mid \exists (\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \text{ such that } i \in \text{out}\} \text{ and} \\ \Lambda_{i,\text{in}}^p(\Gamma) &= \{?\mathbf{m} \mid \exists (\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \text{ such that } i \in \text{in}\}. \end{aligned}$$

A local LTS for i with poor local actions is an LTS $\mathcal{M}_i^p = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, \Lambda_i^p(\Gamma), T_i)$ over $\Lambda_i^p(\Gamma)$.

The notion of a **system with poor local actions** is defined completely analogously to the rich case in Sect. 4.1. Γ -composition with poor local actions needs, however, special care since for matching local actions only the message name and input/output information is relevant. Therefore, the interaction set Γ imposes a structure on the composition of local LTS which resembles the use of connectors for interface-based composition of software components.

Definition 8 (synchronous Γ -composition with poor local actions).

Let $(\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}$ be a family of local LTS $\mathcal{M}_i^p = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, \Lambda_i^p(\Gamma), T_i)$ with poor local actions. The synchronous Γ -composition of $(\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}$ with poor local actions is the global LTS, denoted by $\otimes_{\Gamma}^p(\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}$, over (Σ, Γ) with initial state $(q_{i,0})_{i \in I}$ and with (product) states $(q_i)_{i \in I}$ (such that $q_i \in Q$ for all $i \in I$) and transitions generated from the initial state by the following rule:

$$\frac{(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \quad (\forall i \in \text{out} : q_i \xrightarrow{!\mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i) \quad (\forall i \in \text{in} : q_i \xrightarrow{?\mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i)}{(q_i)_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}^p(\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}} (q'_i)_{i \in I} \text{ where } q'_i = q_i \text{ for all } i \in I \setminus (\text{out} \cup \text{in})}$$

The notion of **realisability with poor local actions** is defined completely analogously to the rich case (cf. Definition 6) replacing “rich (r)” by “poor (p)”. For a concrete realisation with rich local actions in the race example (cf. Sect. 1).

An obvious question is whether realisability with respect to the two different localisation styles can be formally compared. Indeed, it turns out that realisability with poor local actions implies realisability in the rich case but not conversely. First, we show how we can transform a poor realisation into a rich one by stratifying each poor action to a set of rich ones.

Definition 9 (richification). Let $i \in I$ and $\mathcal{M}_i^p = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, \Lambda_i^p(\Gamma), T_i)$ be a local LTS for i with poor local actions. The richification of \mathcal{M}_i^p is the local LTS $r\mathcal{M}_i^p = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, \Lambda_i^r(\Gamma), rT_i)$ with rich local actions where the transitions rT_i are generated by the following rules:

$$\frac{(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \quad q \xrightarrow{\text{!m}}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q' \quad i \in \text{out}}{q \xrightarrow{\text{out in !m}}_{r\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'} \quad \frac{(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \quad q \xrightarrow{?m}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q' \quad i \in \text{in}}{q \xrightarrow{\text{out in ?m}}_{r\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'}$$

Lemma 1. Let $(\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}$ be a family of local LTS $\mathcal{M}_i^p = (Q_i, q_{i,0}, \Lambda_i^p(\Gamma), T_i)$ with poor local actions. Then $\otimes_{\Gamma}^p (\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I} = \otimes_{\Gamma}^r (r\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}$.

Proof. We show that the transition relations are the same.

“ \subseteq ”: Let $(q_i)_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}^p (\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}} (q'_i)_{i \in I}$. Then, by the definition of \otimes_{Γ}^p , we have that $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$, $\forall i \in \text{out} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{!m}}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i$, and $\forall i \in \text{in} : q_i \xrightarrow{?m}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i$. Hence, by the definition of $r\mathcal{M}_i^p$, we have that $\forall i \in \text{out} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{out in !m}}_{r\mathcal{M}_i^p}$, and also $\forall i \in \text{in} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{out in ?m}}_{r\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i$. Then, by the definition of \otimes_{Γ}^r , we have that $(q_i)_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}^r (r\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}} (q'_i)_{i \in I}$.

“ \supseteq ”: Let $(q_i)_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}^r (r\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}} (q'_i)_{i \in I}$. Then, by the definition of \otimes_{Γ}^r , we have that $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$, $\forall i \in \text{out} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{out in !m}}_{r\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i$, and $\forall i \in \text{in} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{out in ?m}}_{r\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i$. Hence, by the definition of $r\mathcal{M}_i^p$, we have that $\forall i \in \text{out} : q_i \xrightarrow{\text{!m}}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i$, and $\forall i \in \text{in} : q_i \xrightarrow{?m}_{\mathcal{M}_i^p} q'_i$. Then, by the definition of \otimes_{Γ}^p , we have that $(q_i)_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}^p (\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}} (q'_i)_{i \in I}$. \square

As an obvious consequence of Lemma 1 we get the following result.

Theorem 2 (poor realisation implies rich realisation). Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) which is realisable by a system $\mathcal{S}^p = (\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}$ with poor local actions. Then \mathcal{M} is realisable by system $\mathcal{S}^r = (r\mathcal{M}_i^p)_{i \in I}$ with rich local actions.

The converse of Theorem 2 is not true, as demonstrated by the next example.

Example 4. We consider a variant of the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}^{\square}$ (Fig. 2) where the transitions $1 \xrightarrow{\text{R2} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish}} 3 \xrightarrow{\text{R1} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish}} 0$ are removed, i.e. the controller enforces an order who has to finish first (R1). Let us call the resulting LTS $\mathcal{M}'_{\text{Race}}^{\square}$. Moreover, consider the variant of the local controller $\mathcal{M}'_{\text{Ctrl}}$ (upper row of Table 1, left) where the local transitions $1 \xrightarrow{\text{R2Ctrl?finish}} 3 \xrightarrow{\text{R1Ctrl?finish}} 0$ are removed and call it $\mathcal{M}'^r_{\text{Ctrl}}$. Now let

$$\mathcal{S}'^r = \{\mathcal{M}'^r_{\text{Ctrl}}, \mathcal{M}'_{\text{R1}}, \mathcal{M}'_{\text{R2}}\}$$

be the system with rich local actions (where $\mathcal{M}'_{\text{R1}}, \mathcal{M}'_{\text{R2}}$ are shown in the upper row of Table 1, middle and right). It is easy to check that \mathcal{S}'^r is a realisation of $\mathcal{M}'_{\text{Race}}^{\square}$ with rich local actions, since $\mathcal{M}'_{\text{Race}}^{\square}$ is even isomorphic to the (rich) Γ_{Race} -composition of $\{\mathcal{M}'^r_{\text{Ctrl}}, \mathcal{M}'_{\text{R1}}, \mathcal{M}'_{\text{R2}}\}$.

The situation is different if we consider the poor case with controller $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Ctrl}}^p$ (lower row of Table 1, left) which accepts two times in a row a “finish” signal but, due to the poor local actions, cannot fix an acceptance order. The only candidate for a realisation with poor local actions is then the system

$$\mathcal{S}'^p = \{\mathcal{M}_{\text{Ctrl}}^p, \mathcal{M}_{R1}^p, \mathcal{M}_{R2}^p\}$$

consisting of the local LTS with poor local actions shown in the lower row of Table 1. Obviously, the Γ_{Race} -composition of these local LTS with poor actions does allow a sequence of transitions $1 \xrightarrow{R2 \rightarrow \text{Ctrl:finish}} 3 \xrightarrow{R1 \rightarrow \text{Ctrl:finish}} 0$ and therefore cannot be bisimilar to $\mathcal{M}'_{\text{Race}}$. \triangleright

5 Realisability Conditions

In general a global LTS may not be realisable. Therefore we are interested in (i) conditions which guarantee realisability and (ii) techniques to synthesise realisations from a global LTS \mathcal{M} . The following notion of I -equivalence provides a helpful tool. The basic idea is that the source and target states of a global transition $q \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'$ are considered to be indistinguishable for a component $i \in I$ if i does not participate in the interaction, i.e. $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$ (cf. also [12] and the discussion below). It turns out that, in general, one has to identify even more global states from the viewpoint of i .

Definition 10 (I -equivalence). Let $\mathcal{M} = (Q, q_0, \Gamma, T)$ be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) . An I -equivalence over \mathcal{M} is a family $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ of equivalence relations $\equiv_i \subseteq Q \times Q$ (reflexive, symmetric, and transitive) such that $q \equiv_i q'$ holds whenever there exists a transition $q \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q'$ with $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. The equivalence class of a state $q \in Q$ w.r.t. \equiv_i is the set $[q]_{\equiv_i} = \{q' \in Q \mid q' \equiv_i q\}$.

5.1 Condition for Realisability Using Rich Local Actions

First, we will formulate our realisability condition for the case of rich local actions. We consider a global LTS \mathcal{M} over (Σ, Γ) . Our goal is to find an I -equivalence $(\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ over \mathcal{M} such that for each interaction $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$ the following holds. Assume, for simplicity, that $\text{out} \cup \text{in} = \{1, \dots, n\}$. Whenever there is a combination q_1, \dots, q_n of n (not necessarily different) global states together with a global “glue” state g , i.e. for each $j \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$, $q_j \equiv_j g$, then we expect: if $\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ is enabled in each global state q_1, \dots, q_n then each $j \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$ should also be able to participate in $\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ when the global state is g , since j cannot distinguish g from q_j . Thus the global interaction $\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ should be enabled in g . Moreover, the execution of the interaction should preserve I -equivalences.

Definition 11 (realisability condition (rich case)). Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) . The realisability condition $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$ for \mathcal{M} with respect to rich local actions says that there exists an I -equivalence $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ over \mathcal{M} such that the following property $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$ holds.

For all $\gamma \in \Gamma$ with participants $\text{ptc}(\gamma) = \{k_1, \dots, k_n\}$ we have:

$$\forall \left(\begin{array}{c} q_1 \xrightarrow{\gamma} \mathcal{M} q'_1 \quad \dots \quad q_n \xrightarrow{\gamma} \mathcal{M} q'_n \\ g \in \bigcap_{j=1}^n [q_j]_{\equiv_{k_j}} \end{array} \right) \quad \exists g' : \left(\begin{array}{c} g \xrightarrow{\gamma} \mathcal{M} g' \\ g' \in \bigcap_{j=1}^n [q'_j]_{\equiv_{k_j}} \end{array} \right)$$

We will provide a constructive proof that the realisability condition $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$ indeed guarantees realisability. For this purpose, we construct local quotients with rich local actions from a given global LTS \mathcal{M} .

Definition 12 (local quotients with rich local actions). Let $\mathcal{M} = (Q, q_0, \Gamma, T)$ be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) and $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ an I -equivalence over \mathcal{M} . For each $i \in I$ the local i -quotient of \mathcal{M} with rich local actions is the LTS $(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r = (Q/\equiv_i, [q_0]_{\equiv_i}, A_i^r(\Gamma), (T/\equiv_i)^r)$ where

- $Q/\equiv_i = \{[q]_{\equiv_i} \mid q \in Q\}$,
- $(T/\equiv_i)^r$ is the least set of transitions generated by the following rules:

$$\frac{q \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} q' \quad i \in \text{out}}{[q]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{out in} ! m} (\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r [q']_{\equiv_i}} \quad \frac{q \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} q' \quad i \in \text{in}}{[q]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{out in} ? m} (\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r [q']_{\equiv_i}}$$

Note that $[q]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{out in} ! m} (\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r [q']_{\equiv_i}$ implies that there exist $\hat{q} \in [q]_{\equiv_i}$, $\hat{q}' \in [q']_{\equiv_i}$ and a transition $\hat{q} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} \hat{q}'$ with $i \in \text{out}$ (and similarly for $\text{out in} ? m$).

Theorem 3. Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) and let $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ be an I -equivalence over \mathcal{M} . If $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$ holds, then $\mathcal{M} \sim \otimes_{\Gamma}^r ((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r)_{i \in I}$.

Corollary 1 (realisability condition sufficient (rich)). Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) . If $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$ holds then \mathcal{M} is realisable with rich local actions.

Proof. Assume that $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$ holds. We define the following relation B between the state space Q of \mathcal{M} and the state space of $\otimes_{\Gamma}^r ((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r)_{i \in I}$, let us call it Q_{\otimes} , consisting of all families $([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$ which are generated by the rules in Definition 12:

$$B = \left\{ (g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \mid g \in Q, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} \in Q_{\otimes}, g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q_i]_{\equiv_i} \right\} \subseteq Q \times Q_{\otimes}.$$

Obviously, $(q_0, ([q_0]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$. To show that B satisfies conditions (1) and (2) of a bisimulation relation (cf. Sect. 2), we proceed as follows. Let $(g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$ and $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m) \in \Gamma$.

(1): Assume $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} g'$. Then, by Definition 12, we have transitions $[g]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{out in} ! m} (\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r [g']_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{out}$ and $[g]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{out in} ? m} (\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r [g']_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{in}$. Moreover, since $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} g'$, we have, by def. of I -equivalence, $g \equiv_i g'$ and therefore $[g]_{\equiv_i} = [g']_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. Then, by Definition 5, $([g]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \otimes_{\Gamma}^r ((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r)_{i \in I} ([g']_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$.

Since $(g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$, we know $g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and thus $([g]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} = ([q]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$. It remains to see that $(g', ([g']_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$, i.e. $g' \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [g']_{\equiv_i}$ which is obvious.

(2): Assume $([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \otimes_{r, ((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r)_{i \in I}} ([q'_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$. According to Definition 5 this can only happen if $[q_i]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{out in}! m} (\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{out}$ and $[q_i]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{out in} ? m} (\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{in}$ and $[q_i]_{\equiv_i} = [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. Hence, by Definition 12, for all $i \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$ there exist $\hat{q}_i \in [q_i]_{\equiv_i}$, $\hat{q}'_i \in [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and transitions $\hat{q}_i \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} \hat{q}'_i$. Since $(g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$, we know $g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and hence also $g \equiv_i \hat{q}_i$ for all $i \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. Now we apply the assumption that $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$ holds. Therefore there exists a transition $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} g'$ such that $g' \equiv_i \hat{q}'_i$ and hence $g' \equiv_i q'_i$ for all $i \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. For all $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$ we know, by def. of I -equivalence and since $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m} \mathcal{M} g'$, that $g \equiv_i g'$ and hence $g' \equiv_i g \equiv_i q_i \equiv_i q'_i$. Thus $g' \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and therefore $(g', ([q'_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$. \square

Having given a global LTS \mathcal{M} instead of looking for a realisation from scratch, the next step of our development method should be to check realisability. For this purpose we must provide an appropriate I -equivalence $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ such that $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$ holds. Once we have found such an equivalence we follow Theorem 3 and construct the local quotients $(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r$ for all $i \in I$. We can now take the system $(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r_{i \in I}$ as our realisation with rich local actions (cf. Fig. 3). As an optimisation we may still want to replace some local LTS by smaller, bisimulation equivalent ones which is sound since Γ -composition with rich local actions preserves bisimilarity. (The proof is straightforward and points out another benefit of using bisimulations.)

Example 5. Consider the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ (Fig. 2). We show that $RC(\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}})^r$ holds and how to construct, following Theorem 3, a realisation of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$. More concretely, we take the family of equivalences $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in \{\text{Ctrl}, \text{R1}, \text{R2}\}}$ that obeys $RC(\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}, \equiv)^r$ (see below) and partitions the state space Q as follows: $Q/\equiv_{\text{Ctrl}} = \{\{0\}, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}\}$, $Q/\equiv_{\text{R1}} = \{\{0, 2\}, \{1, 3\}\}$, and $Q/\equiv_{\text{R2}} = \{\{0, 3\}, \{1, 2\}\}$. Using these equivalences, the local quotients for **R1** and **R2** are as follows:

The local quotient for **Ctrl** is isomorphic to $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ but with local labels. Thus we have obtained a system which is a realisation with rich local actions of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$. The local quotients coincide, up to renaming of states, with the local LTS used in the system $\mathcal{S}_{\text{Race}}^r$ considered in Sect. 1.

Now, we illustrate how to verify $RC(\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}, \equiv)^r$ using, as an example, the interaction $\gamma = \text{R1} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish}$ which appears twice in $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$: $t_{12} = (1 \xrightarrow{\gamma} 2)$ and $t_{30} = (3 \xrightarrow{\gamma} 0)$. There are two participants involved: **R1** and **Ctrl**. Hence we need to consider four combinations: (t_{12}, t_{12}) , (t_{12}, t_{30}) , (t_{30}, t_{12}) , and (t_{30}, t_{30}) . For example, using the combination (t_{30}, t_{12}) , we compute the glue $[3]_{\equiv_{\text{R1}}} \cap [1]_{\equiv_{\text{Ctrl}}} = \{1\}$.

Then, trivially, there exists a transition $1 \xrightarrow{\gamma} 2$, and $2 \in [0]_{\equiv_{R1}} \cap [2]_{\equiv_{C1f}}$. The same can be shown for all the glues found for the other three combinations. \triangleright

Example 6. For the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{TOSS}}$ in Example 3 the realisability condition $RC(\mathcal{M}_{\text{TOSS}})^r$ holds. It can be satisfied for two different I -equivalences. The first one identifies for **Person** the states 1 and 2 of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{TOSS}}$ while identifying nothing for **Coin**. The resulting local quotients are, up to renaming of states, the local LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Person}}^r$ and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Coin}}^r$ shown in Table 2. The second one identifies for **Coin** the states 1 and 2 while identifying nothing for **Person**. It leads to a non-deterministic version of the local LTS for **Person** and a deterministic one for **Coin**. \triangleright

Corollary 1 is a direct consequence of Theorem 3 and the definition of $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$. Let us note that the bisimulation relation B used in the proof of Theorem 3 is a function from the state space of \mathcal{M} to that of $\otimes_{\Gamma}((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^r)_{i \in I}$. First, for each $g \in Q$, $(g, ([g]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$. Now, consider an arbitrary $g \in Q$ and two pairs $(g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$ and $(g, ([q'_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$. Then, by definition of B , $g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and $g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$. Hence $g \equiv_i q_i$ and $g \equiv_i q'_i$ for all $i \in I$. Therefore $q_i \equiv_i q'_i$ for all $i \in I$ and thus $([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} = ([q'_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$.

We claim that the converse of Corollary 1 also holds under the assumption that a functional bisimulation relation can be used to establish the realisation. In general, however, it may happen that a global LTS \mathcal{M} does not satisfy $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$ but nevertheless is realisable, as shown next.

Example 7. Consider the signature $\Sigma = (I, M)$ with $I = \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}$, $M = \{\mathbf{m}\}$ and the set $\Gamma = \{\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{c} \rightarrow \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{c} \rightarrow \mathbf{a} : \mathbf{m}\}$ of Σ -interactions. The global LTS \mathcal{M} in Table 3 (left) is realisable by the system $\mathcal{S}^r = \{\mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{a}}^r, \mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{b}}^r, \mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{c}}^r\}$. To see this, we compute the Γ -composition $\mathcal{M}' = \otimes_{\Gamma} \{\mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{a}}^r, \mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{b}}^r, \mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{c}}^r\}$ shown in Table 3 (right). Obviously \mathcal{M} is bisimilar to \mathcal{M}' and hence \mathcal{M} is realisable. However, \mathcal{M} does not satisfy the realisability condition $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$.

We prove this by contradiction. Assume that $\equiv = \{\equiv_{\mathbf{a}}, \equiv_{\mathbf{b}}, \equiv_{\mathbf{c}}\}$ is an I -equivalence such that $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$ holds. Now consider the interaction $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{m}$, the global state 0 of \mathcal{M} and the transition $0 \xrightarrow{\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} 1$. Obviously, $0 \equiv_{\mathbf{a}} 1$ and $0 \equiv_{\mathbf{b}} 1$ must hold since there is the transition $0 \xrightarrow{\mathbf{c} \rightarrow \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} 1$ where \mathbf{a} does not participate and the transition $0 \xrightarrow{\mathbf{c} \rightarrow \mathbf{a} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} 1$ where \mathbf{b} does not participate. So we can take 1 as a glue state between the global states $q_1 = 0$ and $q_2 = 0$. Then we consider the transition $0 \xrightarrow{\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} 1$ one time for q_1 and one time for q_2 . Since we have assumed $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$, there must be a transition $1 \xrightarrow{\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}'}$ leaving the glue state which is, however, not the case. Contradiction! Note that nevertheless the bisimilar global LTS \mathcal{M}' does satisfy $RC(\mathcal{M}')^r$. The example can be checked at \mathcal{M}^{\boxtimes} and \mathcal{M}'^{\boxtimes} . \triangleright

Discussion Our realisability condition $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$, based on the notion of an I -equivalence $(\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$, is strongly related to a condition for implementability in [12, Theorem 3.1]. In fact, $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$ can be seen as a generalisation of [12] since we take into account multi-interactions with distinguished sets of senders and receivers and also specifications for admissible interactions represented by Γ .

Table 3: Global LTS \mathcal{M} not satisfying $RC(\mathcal{M})^r$ but with realisation $\mathcal{S}^r = \{\mathcal{M}_a^r, \mathcal{M}_b^r, \mathcal{M}_c^r\}$ where $\mathcal{M}' = \otimes^r\{\mathcal{M}_a^r, \mathcal{M}_b^r, \mathcal{M}_c^r\}$

Thus we get a generic realisability notion that is based on Γ -composition instead of full synchronisation. Moreover, our condition ensures realisability modulo bisimulation instead of isomorphism. Technically, implementability with respect to isomorphism is achieved in [12, Theorem 3.1] by requiring that whenever two global states q and q' are i -equivalent, i.e., $(q \equiv_i q')$, for all $i \in I$, then $q = q'$. We do not use this assumption here and thus can get realisations modulo bisimilarity which do not realise a global LTS up to isomorphism (cf. Example 8 below). Note that [12, Theorem 6.2] also provides a proposal to deal with implementability modulo bisimulation under the assumption of “deterministic product transition systems”. In the next section, we study a realisability condition for the case of poor local actions, which deviates significantly from [12].

Example 8. There is a simple example for a situation in which a global LTS satisfies our realisability condition but there is no realisation up to isomorphism. Let $\Sigma = (I, M)$ with $I = \{a, b\}$ and $M = \{m\}$ and let $\Gamma = \{a \rightarrow \emptyset : m, b \rightarrow \emptyset : m\}$ be the interaction set. Let \mathcal{M} be the global LTS with states 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 (initial state 0) and transitions $0 \xrightarrow{a \rightarrow \emptyset : m} \mathcal{M} 1 \xrightarrow{b \rightarrow \emptyset : m} \mathcal{M} 2$ and $0 \xrightarrow{b \rightarrow \emptyset : m} \mathcal{M} 3 \xrightarrow{a \rightarrow \emptyset : m} \mathcal{M} 4$. As equivalences for a and b we take the reflexive, symmetric and transitive closures of $1 \equiv_a 2$, $0 \equiv_a 3$, and $1 \equiv_a 4$ and of $0 \equiv_b 1$, $3 \equiv_b 4$, and $2 \equiv_b 3$. Note that $1 \equiv_a 4$ and $2 \equiv_b 3$ are enforced to satisfy $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^r$. By symmetry and transitivity we also get $2 \equiv_a 4$ and $2 \equiv_b 4$. Since the realisability condition holds, \mathcal{M} is realisable with rich local actions up to bisimilarity. However, \mathcal{M} is not realisable up to isomorphism. Otherwise, states 2 and 4 should be the same (cf. [12, Theorem 3.1]).

Another example satisfying our realisability condition with respect to rich local actions but which is not realisable up to isomorphism is here: **Cast-v1** (RC^r holds) $\color{red}\boxtimes$ ▷

5.2 Condition for Realisability Using Poor Local Actions

We return to the question of how to check realisability, now in the case of poor local actions. The notion of I -equivalence is again the key. Note, however, that the computation of an appropriate I -equivalence may differ from the rich case.

The realisability condition below is stronger than the one for rich local actions in [Definition 11](#). Intuitively, the reason is that local LTS with poor local actions have, in general, more choices for synchronisation and therefore a global LTS must support these choices in order to be realisable. For each interaction $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$, we require in more cases the enabledness in a glue state g . More concretely, $\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}$ must be enabled in g already when in the j -equivalent states, say q_j , component j is able to output/input message m independently of the communication partners named in $\text{out} \cup \text{in}$, since those would anyway not be known from a poor local action. This is formally reflected by considering the interactions $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n$ in the next definition.

Definition 13 (realisability condition (poor case)). *Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) . The realisability condition $RC(\mathcal{M})^{\text{P}}$ for \mathcal{M} with respect to poor local actions says that there exists an I -equivalence $(\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ over \mathcal{M} such that the following property $RC(\mathcal{M}, (\equiv_i)_{i \in I})^{\text{P}}$ holds.*

For all $\gamma = (\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma$ with participants $\text{ptc}(\gamma) = \{k_1, \dots, k_n\}$ we get:

$$\forall \left(\begin{array}{l} \gamma_1 = (\text{out}_1 \rightarrow \text{in}_1 : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \\ k_1 \in (\text{out}_1 \cap \text{out}) \cup (\text{in}_1 \cap \text{in}) \\ \dots \\ \gamma_n = (\text{out}_n \rightarrow \text{in}_n : \mathbf{m}) \in \Gamma \\ k_n \in (\text{out}_n \cap \text{out}) \cup (\text{in}_n \cap \text{in}) \end{array} \right) \quad \forall \left(\begin{array}{l} q_1 \xrightarrow{\gamma_1}_{\mathcal{M}} q'_1 \\ \dots \\ q_n \xrightarrow{\gamma_n}_{\mathcal{M}} q'_n \\ g \in \bigcap_{j=1}^n [q_j]_{\equiv_{k_j}} \end{array} \right) \quad \exists g' : \left(\begin{array}{l} g \xrightarrow{\gamma}_{\mathcal{M}} g' \\ g' \in \bigcap_{j=1}^n [q'_j]_{\equiv_{k_j}} \end{array} \right)$$

To prove that the condition $RC(\mathcal{M})^{\text{P}}$ indeed guarantees realisability with poor local actions, the idea is again to consider local quotients. Their construction is, however, different from the rich case.

Definition 14 (local quotients with poor local actions). *Let $\mathcal{M} = (Q, q_0, \Gamma, T)$ be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) and $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ an I -equivalence over \mathcal{M} . For each $i \in I$ the local i -quotient of \mathcal{M} with poor local actions is the LTS $(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\text{P}} = (Q/\equiv_i, [q_0]_{\equiv_i}, \Lambda_i^{\text{P}}(\Gamma), (T/\equiv_i)^{\text{P}})$ where*

- $Q/\equiv_i = \{[q]_{\equiv_i} \mid q \in Q\}$,
- $(T/\equiv_i)^{\text{P}}$ is the least set of transitions generated by the following rules:

$$\frac{q \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q' \quad i \in \text{out}}{[q]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{! \mathbf{m}}_{(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\text{P}}} [q']_{\equiv_i}} \quad \frac{q \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : \mathbf{m}}_{\mathcal{M}} q' \quad i \in \text{in}}{[q]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{? \mathbf{m}}_{(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\text{P}}} [q']_{\equiv_i}}$$

Theorem 4. *Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) and let $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ be an I -equivalence over \mathcal{M} . If $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^{\text{P}}$ holds then $\mathcal{M} \sim \otimes_{\Gamma}^{\text{P}} ((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\text{P}})_{i \in I}$.*

Corollary 2 (realisability condition sufficient (poor)). *Let \mathcal{M} be a global LTS over (Σ, Γ) . If $RC(\mathcal{M})^{\text{P}}$ holds then \mathcal{M} is realisable with poor local actions.*

Proof. Assume that $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^{\mathsf{P}}$ holds. Like in the rich case we define the following relation B between the state space Q of \mathcal{M} and the state space of $\otimes_{\Gamma}((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}})_{i \in I}$, let us call it Q_{\otimes} , consisting of all families $([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$ which are generated by the rules in [Definition 12](#):

$$B = \left\{ (g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \mid g \in Q, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} \in Q_{\otimes}, g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q_i]_{\equiv_i} \right\} \subseteq Q \times Q_{\otimes}.$$

Obviously, $(q_0, ([q_0]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$. To show that B satisfies conditions (1) and (2) of a bisimulation relation (cf. [Sect. 2](#)), we proceed as follows. Let $(g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$ and $(\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m) \in \Gamma$.

(1): Assume $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m}_{\mathcal{M}} g'$. Then, by [Definition 14](#), we have transitions $[g]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{!m}}_{(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}}} [g']_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{out}$ and $[g]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{?m}_{(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}}} [g']_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{in}$. Moreover, since $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m}_{\mathcal{M}} g'$, we have, by def. of I -equivalence, $g \equiv_i g'$ and therefore $[g]_{\equiv_i} = [g']_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. Then, by [Definition 8](#), $([g]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}})_{i \in I}} ([g']_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$. Since $(g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$, we know $g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and thus $([g]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} = ([q]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$. It remains to see that $(g', ([g']_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$, i.e. $g' \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [g']_{\equiv_i}$ which is obvious.

(2): Assume $([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I} \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m}_{\otimes_{\Gamma}((\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}})_{i \in I}} ([q'_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}$. According to [Definition 8](#) this can only happen if $[q_i]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{\text{!m}}_{(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}}} [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{out}$ and $[q_i]_{\equiv_i} \xrightarrow{?m}_{(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}}} [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \in \text{in}$ and $[q_i]_{\equiv_i} = [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ for all $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. Hence, by [Definition 14](#), for all $i \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$ there exist: $\gamma_i = (\text{out}_i \rightarrow \text{in}_i : m) \in \Gamma$ (such that $i \in \text{out}_i$ if $i \in \text{out}$, $i \in \text{in}_i$ if $i \in \text{in}_i$), $\hat{q}_i \in [q_i]_{\equiv_i}$, $\hat{q}'_i \in [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$, and transitions $\hat{q}_i \xrightarrow{\text{out}_i \rightarrow \text{in}_i : m}_{\mathcal{M}} \hat{q}'_i$. Since $(g, ([q_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$, we know $g \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and hence also $g \equiv_i \hat{q}_i$ for all $i \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. Now we apply the assumption that $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^{\mathsf{P}}$ holds. Therefore there exists a transition $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m}_{\mathcal{M}} g'$ such that $g' \equiv_i \hat{q}'_i$ and hence $g' \equiv_i q'_i$ for all $i \in \text{out} \cup \text{in}$. For all $i \notin \text{out} \cup \text{in}$ we know, by def. of I -equivalence and since $g \xrightarrow{\text{out} \rightarrow \text{in} : m}_{\mathcal{M}} g'$, that $g \equiv_i g'$ and hence $g' \equiv_i g \equiv_i q_i \equiv_i q'_i$. Thus $g' \in \bigcap_{i \in I} [q'_i]_{\equiv_i}$ and therefore $(g', ([q'_i]_{\equiv_i})_{i \in I}) \in B$. \square

Having given a global LTS \mathcal{M} also in the poor case our development method continues by checking the realisability condition, now $RC(\mathcal{M})^{\mathsf{P}}$. Again we must provide an appropriate I -equivalence $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in I}$ such that $RC(\mathcal{M}, \equiv)^{\mathsf{P}}$ holds. Once we have found such an equivalence we follow [Theorem 4](#) and construct the local quotients $(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}}$ for all $i \in I$. We can now take the system $(\mathcal{M}/\equiv_i)^{\mathsf{P}}_{i \in I}$ as our realisation with poor local actions. Again an optimisation of the local LTS may be possible by replacing them by bisimilar ones. Also Γ -composition with poor local actions preserves bisimilarity. (The proof is straightforward.)

Example 9. Consider the global LTS $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ ([Fig. 2](#)). We show $RC(\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}})^{\mathsf{P}}$ holds and how, following [Theorem 4](#), a realisation of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$ with poor local actions can be constructed. The situation differs from the rich case in [Example 5](#), since the equivalence for **Ctrl** must be chosen differently. We use the family of equivalences $\equiv = (\equiv_i)_{i \in \{\text{Ctrl}, \text{R1}, \text{R2}\}}$ that obeys $RC(\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}, \equiv)^{\mathsf{P}}$ (see below) and

partitions the state space Q as follows: $Q/\equiv_{\text{Ctrl}} = \{\{0\}, \{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$, $Q/\equiv_{\text{R1}} = \{\{0, 2\}, \{1, 3\}\}$, and $Q/\equiv_{\text{R2}} = \{\{0, 3\}, \{1, 2\}\}$. Using these equivalences, the local quotients for **Ctrl**, **R1** and **R2** are as follows:

Thus we have obtained a system which is a realisation with poor local actions of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}$. The local quotients coincide, up to renaming of states, with the local LTS used in the system $\mathcal{S}_{\text{Race}}^{\text{P}}$ considered in Sect. 1.

Now, we illustrate how to verify $RC(\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}, \equiv)^r$ using, as an example, the interaction **R1** \rightarrow **Ctrl** : **finish**. We have $1 \xrightarrow{\text{R1} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish}}_{\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}} 2$. We also have $1 \xrightarrow{\text{R2} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish}}_{\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}} 3$ (we must consider the interaction **R2** \rightarrow **Ctrl** : **finish** as well since we are in the poor case). Taking 1 as a (trivial) glue state, we thus have, as required, the existence of $1 \xrightarrow{\text{R1} \rightarrow \text{Ctrl} : \text{finish}}_{\mathcal{M}_{\text{Race}}} 2$ but also it is required that $2 \equiv_{\text{Ctrl}} 3$ must hold which is the case. Note that we wouldn't have succeeded here if we would have taken the identity for \equiv_{Ctrl} as done for the rich case. \triangleright

6 Tool Support: Ceta

We developed a supporting prototypical tool *Ceta* (Choreographic Extended Team Automata) to analyse global specifications and produce visualisations of state machines. It is open-source, available at <https://github.com/arcabab/choreo/tree/ceta>, and executable by browsing to <https://lmf.di.uminho.pt/ceta>.

Using Ceta *Ceta* starts with a web browser, opening a static webpage that uses our compiled JavaScript built with the Caos framework [32] (cf. screenshot in Fig. 4). The user input is a global protocol described in a choreographic language, resembling regular expressions of interactions. A set of examples with descriptions is also included, covering the examples presented in this paper. The analyses are on the right and below and include graphical views of: (i) the global LTS; (ii) local LTS's with rich actions; and (iii) local LTS's with poor actions. Other widgets provide further insights, such as the composition of the local LTS's, the intermediate equivalence classes for both the rich and poor cases, the synchronous composition of local LTS's, and bisimulations between the global protocol and composed systems. Readable error messages are provided when the realisability conditions do not hold.

Note on Complexity *Ceta* provides a *constructive* approach to the *declarative* description of the realisability conditions (cf. Definitions 11 and 13). It builds a family of equivalence relations, starting with one that groups states connected by indistinguishable transitions (in which the associate participant is not involved).

Fig. 4: Screenshot of the Ceta tool (<http://lmf.di.uminho.pt/ceta>)

This building process uses the set of global actions Γ as the set of the labels on all transitions T from reachable states. In the *rich case*, for each of these actions $\gamma \in \Gamma$, it proceeds as follows: (i) collect the set of \underline{n} involved participants; (ii) collect the set $T' \subseteq T$ of all \underline{t} transitions that have label γ ; (iii) find all \underline{t}^n combinations of transitions $\sigma \in T'$ for each participant; (iv) find all glue states g that belong to all equivalence classes of the sources of the transitions σ ; (v) check if every glue g has an outgoing transition labelled by γ (if not, the realisability condition fails); and (vi) check if any of the target states from g is equivalent to the destinations of σ for the respective participants (if not, extend the equivalence relation). After traversing the actions in Γ , if the equivalence relation was extended in (vi), then the process is repeated, since new glue states may be found in (iv). If no failure occurs, then the realisability condition is satisfied and the resulting equivalence classes are used to join equivalent states in the global LTS, yielding local quotients.

We observe that the overall complexity stays in $\mathcal{O}(\underline{t}^n)$ for the *rich case*, considering the largest number t of transitions and n of participants found in this process. The repetition of these 6 steps, when the equivalence relations are extended in (vi), adds an extra complexity, but it does not increase the exponential asymptotic upper bound found. In the *poor case* the complexity is similar, but for a possibly larger number t of transitions. These include also transitions labelled by interactions with *the same message and different participants* that involve the i^{th} relevant participant. Hence worst-case scenarios have many equal (rich case) or similar (poor case) labels, and these involve a large number of participants. Furthermore, when the starting point is a choreography or another language with a well-defined operational semantics, the size of the global state space may grow exponentially with the number of concurrent actions [16].

7 Conclusion

We have proposed a rigorous discipline for developing interaction-based systems. At the heart of our methodology lies the realisation of a global interaction model, i.e. its decomposition into a set of (possibly distributed) components with synchronous communication. We have investigated realisability conditions for two different localisation styles (rich and poor local actions) and techniques to synthesise realisations. Our approach is generic with respect to the choice of admissible interaction sets which may contain arbitrary interactions between multiple senders and receivers but may also be restricted, e.g., to various forms of communication, like multicast or peer-to-peer communication. Due to the generic nature of our notion of an interaction set, our results can be instantiated by different concrete coordination formalisms. For instance, synchronisation type specifications used in the framework of (extended) team automata [4] as well as interactions used in BIP [9] can be represented by interaction sets. Our results should then be directly applicable, to extend the team automata framework as well as BIP by global LTS and to generate distributed component systems for them on the basis of our realisation conditions.

In future research, we plan to (i) integrate the treatment of internal actions using weak bisimulation equivalence for the realisation notions; (ii) consider communication properties (like receptiveness and responsiveness, cf. [4]) when systems are generated from global models; (iii) study open global models (systems) and their composition; and (iv) investigate realisability conditions in the context of asynchronous communication. Moreover, we are still looking for a weaker version of our realisability condition for synchronous systems making it necessary for arbitrary (also non-functional) bisimulations.

Furthermore, we intend to investigate the relation with work in the literature on the decomposition of related formalisms like (Petri net or algebraic) processes into (indecomposable) components [27, 31] used to parallelise (verification of) concurrent systems [14, 17] or obtain better (optimised) implementations [33, 34].

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